

Supplementary material for “Heralded quantum non-Gaussian states in pulsed levitating optomechanics”

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I. LEVITATED OPTOMECHANICS HAMILTONIAN

The cavity-based configuration we consider in this work is assumed to realize the coherent-scattering-based coupling of the center-of-mass motion of the NP and the cavity optical mode. For simplicity, here we consider the motion of the NP in only one direction. The interaction Hamiltonian corresponding to this coupling reads [1]

$$H/\hbar = \Delta a^\dagger a + \frac{p_m^2}{2m} + \frac{1}{2}m\omega_m^2 x_m^2 - G(a + a^\dagger)x_m, \quad (\text{S1})$$

where x_m, p_m are the position and momentum of the NP ($[x_m, p_m] = i\hbar$) with mass m and frequency ω_m , a is the annihilation operator of the cavity mode, and G is the optomechanical coupling rate. The frequency ω_m is defined by the properties of the trapping light beam:

$$\omega_m = \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon_c}{\rho W_t^2}} \sqrt{\frac{4P_t}{\pi c \mathcal{A}}}, \quad (\text{S2})$$

where c is the speed of light in vacuum, $\epsilon_c = 3(\epsilon - 1)/(\epsilon + 2)$, ϵ is the relative permittivity of the NP’s material, ρ is the mass density of the NP. Furthermore, W_t is the tweezer waist, \mathcal{A} is the tweezer cross-section area in the waist, P_t is the tweezer power.

The coupling rate G is given by

$$G = \epsilon_c V \sqrt{\frac{4P_t}{\pi c \mathcal{A}}} \sqrt{\frac{\omega_c}{2\hbar V_c}}. \quad (\text{S3})$$

Here V is the NP’s volume, ω_c is the cavity frequency, $V_c = \pi W_c^2 L_c/4$ is the cavity mode volume determined by the cavity waist W_c and length L_c .

Without a cavity, the optomechanical coupling in the free space is given by the coupling rate [2]

$$\Gamma = 2\pi \frac{\alpha k}{\hbar} \sqrt{\frac{7\pi\hbar\omega_m^3}{15\epsilon_0(2\pi c)^3}} \frac{\hbar}{2m\omega_m} \sqrt{\frac{4P_t}{\pi\epsilon_0 c \mathcal{A}}}. \quad (\text{S4})$$

Here $\alpha = \epsilon_0 \epsilon_c V$ is the NP’s polarizability, ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity, $k = \omega_c/c$ is the light wave vector.

II. TIME-DEPENDENT DRIFT MATRIX

In the main text, we have considered the dynamics of the system under the rotating wave approximation (RWA), which simplifies the equations of motion by neglecting the rapidly oscillating terms. The validity of the RWA rests upon the assumptions of good sideband resolution ($\omega_m \gg \kappa$) and weak optomechanical coupling ($g \ll \kappa, \omega_m$). Given that a rather strong optomechanical coupling is available with levitated NPs (e.g. $g/\kappa \approx 0.6$ was reached in [3]),

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FIG. S1. Single phonon probability of the heralded mechanical state as a function of sideband parameter for fixed pulse duration $\kappa\tau = 2$. Red and blue curves correspond to the red and blue detuning, respectively. Dashed lines correspond to a fixed heating rate $\gamma\bar{n} = 0.01\kappa$ while the solid lines correspond to $\gamma\bar{n} = 0.06\kappa$, (a) $n_0 = 0.01$ and (b) $n_0 = 0.1$. (c) Single phonon probability as a function of pulse duration. $\omega_m = 3\kappa$, $\gamma\bar{n} = 0.01\kappa$. Dashed lines are numerical solutions without RWA and solid lines are with considering RWA. The dotted black line is the absolute threshold of single-phonon quantum non-Gaussianity.

here we analyze the optomechanical dynamics beyond RWA. We introduce a time-dependent optomechanical coupling rate $g(t)$. This coupling rate modulates the interaction strength between the optical and mechanical modes. The Hamiltonian of the system in the rotating frame, without invoking the RWA, contains terms oscillating as $\exp[\pm 2i\omega_m t]$. The inclusion of these terms or considering a time-dependent coupling rate leads to a time-dependent drift matrix $\mathbf{D}(t)$. To include the effect of counter-rotating terms we use the linearized optomechanical Hamiltonian of Eq. (1). The equations of motion then arise as

$$\frac{d\mathbf{r}}{dt} = \mathbf{D}^\pm \mathbf{r} + \mathbf{N}\mathbf{r}_{\text{in}}, \quad (\text{S5})$$

Since we are interested in the solution for the pulses of the leaking light we take a derivative of Eq. (17) over time. That is, we have introduced $\mathbf{r}(t) = [b^\dagger, a^\dagger, (\mathcal{A}_{\text{out}}^\pm)^\dagger(\tau), b, a, \mathcal{A}_{\text{out}}^\pm]^T$ as the vector of system operators, and $\mathbf{N}\mathbf{r}_{\text{in}}$ its corresponding vector of noises. The drift matrices for blue and red detuning are

$$\mathbf{D}^+ = \begin{bmatrix} -\gamma & -ige^{-2i\omega_m t} & 0 & 0 & -ig & 0 \\ -ige^{-2i\omega_m t} & -\kappa & 0 & -ig & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sqrt{2\kappa}f_{\text{out}}(t) & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & ig & 0 & -\gamma & ige^{2i\omega_m t} & 0 \\ ig & 0 & 0 & ige^{2i\omega_m t} & -\kappa & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \sqrt{2\kappa}f_{\text{out}}(t) & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{S6})$$

$$\mathbf{D}^- = \begin{bmatrix} -\gamma & -ig & 0 & 0 & -ige^{-2i\omega_m t} & 0 \\ -ig & -\kappa & 0 & -ige^{-2i\omega_m t} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sqrt{2\kappa}f_{\text{out}}(t) & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & ige^{2i\omega_m t} & 0 & -\gamma & ig & 0 \\ ige^{2i\omega_m t} & 0 & 0 & ig & -\kappa & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \sqrt{2\kappa}f_{\text{out}}(t) & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{S7})$$

with the matrix

$$\mathbf{N} = \begin{bmatrix} \sqrt{2\gamma} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sqrt{2\kappa} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -f_{\text{out}}(t) & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \sqrt{2\gamma} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \sqrt{2\kappa} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -f_{\text{out}}(t) & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{S8})$$

The system is then completely described by a 6×6 covariance matrix defined as

$$\mathbf{W}_{jk}(\tau) = \frac{1}{2} \langle \mathbf{r}_j(\tau) \mathbf{r}_k^\dagger(\tau) + \mathbf{r}_k^\dagger(\tau) \mathbf{r}_j(\tau) \rangle. \quad (\text{S9})$$

The evolution of the covariance matrix $\mathbf{W}(t)$ of this three-mode system is governed by the Lyapunov equation [4]:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \mathbf{W}(t) = \mathbf{D}(t) \mathbf{W}(t) + \mathbf{W}(t) \mathbf{D}^\dagger(t) + \mathbf{F}, \quad (\text{S10})$$

where \mathbf{F} is the diffusion matrix,

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \tilde{\mathbf{F}} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{F}} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \text{where } \tilde{\mathbf{F}} = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma(2\bar{n} + 1) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \kappa & -\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{2\kappa} f_{\text{out}}(t) \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{2\kappa} f_{\text{out}}(t) & \frac{1}{2} f_{\text{out}}(t)^2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{S11})$$

accounting for the noise correlations. To trace out the intracavity mode, we remove the rows and columns associated with mode a from the covariance matrix \mathbf{W} . This leaves us with the (4×4) block \mathbf{V} that corresponds to the mechanical mode and the output optical mode given by Eq. (27). Then, we can calculate the desired parameters numerically in the same manner as before.

Fig. (S1) illustrates the probability of generating a single phonon state in the mechanical system as a function of the sideband parameter κ/ω_m . The solid and dashed curves correspond to different levels of mechanical heating. The red (blue) curves are for a red (blue) detuned laser. For blue detuning, the probability is almost constant. For the red detuning, the probability of obtaining a single phonon increases as the sideband parameter increases, until it reaches a maximum value. In the red detuning scenario with a lower heating rate of $\gamma\bar{n} = 0.01\kappa$ (dashed curves), the maximum single phonon probability approaches a larger value compared to the case with a higher heating rate of $\gamma\bar{n} = 0.06\kappa$ (solid curves). This highlights the detrimental effects of thermal decoherence. Beyond the RWA, the interaction between a mechanical mode and an optical mode, which is initially prepared in its vacuum state, can be described by Hamiltonian $H_{\text{BRWA}} = -g(a + a^\dagger)(b + b^\dagger)$. By applying a unitary transformation $U(t) = \exp(igtH_{\text{BRWA}})$, we can obtain the time evolution of the system. This process can be understood as the action of the unitary transformation on the two input modes, resulting in the creation of the desired state. That is

$$\begin{aligned} & U(t) \rho^m(0) \otimes |0\rangle\langle 0| U^\dagger(t) \\ & \approx \rho^m(0) \otimes |0\rangle\langle 0| + g^2 t^2 [b \rho^m(0) b^\dagger + b^\dagger \rho^m(0) b] \otimes |1\rangle\langle 1| \\ & \quad + igt (b \rho^m(0) \otimes |1\rangle\langle 0| - \rho^m(0) b^\dagger \otimes |0\rangle\langle 1|) \\ & \quad + igt (b^\dagger \rho^m(0) \otimes |1\rangle\langle 0| - \rho^m(0) b \otimes |0\rangle\langle 1|). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S12})$$

If we detect a photon in the output optical mode, the mechanical state is projected into

$$\rho_B \propto b \rho^m(0) b^\dagger + b^\dagger \rho^m(0) b. \quad (\text{S13})$$

For very low thermal phonons (as in Fig. S1), the initial mechanical state can be approximated as a vacuum state $\rho^m(0) \approx |0\rangle\langle 0|$. Therefore, we can neglect the first term, and the conditionally generated mechanical state can be approximated as a phonon-added state.

In Fig. S1 (c), we plot the single phonon probability as a function of pulse duration for a fixed value of the sideband ratio. We observe that the results of considering the RWA exactly match those beyond the RWA for blue detuning, as well as for long red-detuned pulses. However, for short red-detuned pulses, they do not match.

Using the same procedure, we have checked that a time-dependent optomechanical coupling rate as $g(t) = \bar{g}[1 - \exp(-\kappa t)]$ will not affect the results of the main text.

FIG. S2. Probability of detecting a single photon at the output with unit detection efficiency after applying the readout pulse. The mechanical state is a phonon-added state generated from the initial mechanical thermal state with (a) $n_0 = 0.01$ and (b) $n_0 = 0.1$. The dotted, dashed, and solid lines correspond to a fixed heating rate $\gamma\bar{n} = 0$, $\gamma\bar{n} = 0.01\kappa$, and $\gamma\bar{n} = 0.06\kappa$, respectively. (c) Maximum single photon detection probability versus detection efficiency for the states generated in (a) and (b). Here we fix the optomechanical interaction coupling rate $g/\kappa = 0.6$.

III. DETAILS ON MEASUREMENT AND VERIFICATION SCHEME

The generated mechanical state is relatively robust against decoherence and noise on timescales comparable to the mechanical decoherence time. Here, we study the readout of the generated mechanical state by applying another optical pulse as shown in Fig. 1 (c). By adjusting the parameters of the second laser pulse, the resulting mechanical state can be measured through photon detection at the output. This process is based on the beam-splitter interaction Hamiltonian of Eq. (4). By adjusting the duration τ_2 and optomechanical interaction rate g of the second optical pulse and assuming the mode $\mathcal{A}_{\text{in}}^-$ is in a vacuum state, then detecting n photons in $\mathcal{A}_{\text{out}}^-$ implies that n phonons have been subtracted from the initial mechanical mode $b(\tau_1)$. This allows the realization of a phonon subtraction operation on the mechanical state. It also indicates that, within the chosen range of parameters, the second pulse's output light provides a direct measurement of the mechanical state's behavior. By determining the probabilities of photon detection, all elements of the mechanical covariance matrix and, consequently, the mechanical density matrix can be identified. We can obtain the measurement probability $p(n)$ starting from a Gaussian state by performing a trace of the unnormalized density operator $\tilde{\rho}_B(n)$, which corresponds to integrating the unnormalized Wigner function Eq. (29). The integration over α leading to the following photon detection probability

$$p(n) = \frac{\mathcal{P}_0}{n! \sqrt{\det(\mathbf{I}_2 - \mathbf{X}_2 \mathbf{R}_{mm})}} \frac{\partial^{2n}}{\partial \alpha_2^n \partial \beta_2^{*n}} e^{\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{s}_c^T \mathbf{A}_p \mathbf{s}_c} |_{\mathbf{s}_c=0}, \quad (\text{S14})$$

with

$$\mathbf{A}_p = \mathbf{R}_{cc} + \mathbf{R}_{cm} (\mathbf{I}_2 - \mathbf{X}_2 \mathbf{R}_{mm})^{-1} \mathbf{X}_2 \mathbf{R}_{mc}. \quad (\text{S15})$$

Since the generated mechanical state is not a Gaussian state, write it in terms of Gaussian states according to Eq. (10). This allows us to calculate the Wigner function of the optical mode at the output. We can calculate the probability of detecting a photon according to

$$p(n) = \frac{f_1 \mathcal{P}_0^1}{n! \sqrt{\det(\mathbf{I}_2 - \mathbf{X}_2 \mathbf{R}_{mm}^1)}} \frac{\partial^{2n}}{\partial \alpha_2^n \partial \beta_2^{*n}} e^{\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{s}_c^T \mathbf{A}_p^1 \mathbf{s}_c} |_{\mathbf{s}_c=0} + \frac{f_2 \mathcal{P}_0^2}{n! \sqrt{\det(\mathbf{I}_2 - \mathbf{X}_2 \mathbf{R}_{mm}^2)}} \frac{\partial^{2n}}{\partial \alpha_2^n \partial \beta_2^{*n}} e^{\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{s}_c^T \mathbf{A}_p^2 \mathbf{s}_c} |_{\mathbf{s}_c=0}, \quad (\text{S16})$$

where \mathbf{R}_{mm}^i and \mathbf{A}_p^i are calculated in terms of covariance matrices \mathbf{V}^i . The effect of detector efficiency can be modeled by inserting a beam splitter of transmissivity η . The output field \mathcal{A}_{out} , which contains information from the

mechanics, is superimposed on the field from an ancillary mode \mathcal{A}_{anc} at a lossless beam-splitter with transmissivity η . Then denoting the two out-modes $\mathcal{A}'_{\text{out}}$ and $\mathcal{A}'_{\text{anc}}$, respectively, we have

$$\mathcal{A}'_{\text{out}} = \sqrt{\eta}\mathcal{A}_{\text{out}} + i\sqrt{1-\eta}\mathcal{A}_{\text{anc}}, \quad (\text{S17})$$

$$\mathcal{A}'_{\text{anc}} = i\sqrt{1-\eta}\mathcal{A}_{\text{out}} + \sqrt{\eta}\mathcal{A}_{\text{anc}}. \quad (\text{S18})$$

This transformation comprises $\mathcal{A}'_{\text{out}} = U^\dagger \mathcal{A}_{\text{out}} U$ and $\mathcal{A}'_{\text{anc}} = U^\dagger \mathcal{A}_{\text{anc}} U$ with $U = e^{i\pi J_3/2} e^{-2i\theta J_2/2} e^{-i\pi J_3/2}$ and the operators

$$J_2 = \frac{1}{2i} [\mathcal{A}'_{\text{anc}} \mathcal{A}'_{\text{out}} - \mathcal{A}'_{\text{out}} \mathcal{A}'_{\text{anc}}] \quad (\text{S19})$$

$$J_3 = \frac{1}{2} [\mathcal{A}'_{\text{anc}} \mathcal{A}'_{\text{anc}} - \mathcal{A}'_{\text{out}} \mathcal{A}'_{\text{out}}]. \quad (\text{S20})$$

We consider the optical state before the beam-splitter ρ_B and the vacuum for the ancillary optical mode. Therefore, the system in the state $\rho = \rho_{\text{out}} \otimes |0\rangle\langle 0|$ will transform according to $\rho' = U\rho U^\dagger$. The output state after the interaction is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \rho' = \sum_{m,n=0} \left[\frac{e^{-i(m-n)\pi/2}}{\sqrt{m!n!}} (-1)^{m+n} (1-\eta)^{\frac{m+n}{2}} \eta^{-\frac{m+n}{2}} \right. \\ \left. \times \mathcal{A}_{\text{out}}^m \eta^{\frac{1}{2}} \mathcal{A}'_{\text{out}} \mathcal{A}_{\text{out}} \rho_{\text{out}} \eta^{\frac{1}{2}} \mathcal{A}'_{\text{out}} \mathcal{A}_{\text{out}} \mathcal{A}_{\text{out}}^{\dagger n} \otimes |m\rangle\langle n| \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S21})$$

We then trace out the ancillary mode $\rho'_{\text{out}} = \text{Tr}_{\text{anc}}[\rho']$ and project into the Fock states to obtain different elements of the output density matrix according to

$$p'_{i,j} = \sum_{l=0} \frac{1}{l!} \sqrt{\frac{(i+l)!(j+l)!}{i!j!}} (1-\eta)^l \eta^{\frac{i+j}{2}} p_{i+l,j+l}. \quad (\text{S22})$$

Specifically, the diagonal elements which give the photon detection probabilities are given by

$$p'_{i,i} = \sum_{l=0} \binom{i+l}{l} (1-\eta)^l \eta^i p_{i+l,i+l}. \quad (\text{S23})$$

The transfer of non-Gaussianity from the mechanical mode to the optical mode is quantified by the non-Gaussianity parameter p_1 . The detection schemes for the generated non-Gaussian mechanical states follow similar principles, irrespective of whether the states are phonon-added or phonon-subtracted. For illustrative purposes, in Fig. S2 we focus on the phonon-added case, with the understanding that analogous considerations apply to the phonon-subtracted scenario. Panels (a) and (b) correspond to the probability of detecting a single photon at the output with unit detection efficiency after applying the readout pulse for various different values of mechanical heating rate. These plots suggest the effects of mechanical heating on the transfer of non-Gaussianity as a key factor. Comparing the (a) blue and (b) red curves, one finds that the non-Gaussianity is reduced by increasing the initial thermal phonons of the mechanical mode. This highlights the challenge of maintaining high non-Gaussianity in the presence of thermal phonons (compare red and blue) and heating rate. Besides, inevitable detection inefficiencies and losses can obscure these non-Gaussian traits, effectively convolving the true photon statistics with a Gaussian noise profile. The non-Gaussianity parameter is highest at the state swap time, $\tau_s \approx \pi/2|G^-|$, where the mechanical and optical modes exchange their quantum states. To investigate the effect of inefficiency, in Fig. S2 (c), we show the maximum single photon detection probability versus detection efficiency for the states generated in Fig. 2 (b). Moreover, if the detection efficiency is reduced to below $\eta < 0.5$ even in the perfect case shown by dotted lines, the non-Gaussianity of the mechanical mode cannot be transferred to the optical mode. We should notice that these results are obtained in a different regime of parameters than the generation part, with a longer pulse duration $\kappa\tau \approx 4$ and a stronger optomechanical coupling $g/\kappa = 0.6$. This suggests that the optimal parameters for state generation and state transfer may be different, and careful optimization is required to achieve high non-Gaussianity in both processes. We note that the insights gleaned from the phonon-added state are extendable to its subtracted counterpart, affirming the symmetry in their non-Gaussian character and detection methodology.

IV. ELEMENTS OF THE MATRIX \mathbf{M}^\pm

The nonzero elements of the matrix \mathbf{M}^\pm are given by

$$\mathbf{M}_{11}^\pm = \mathbf{M}_{33}^\pm = e^{-\frac{1}{2}(\gamma+\kappa)\tau} \left[\cosh G^\pm \tau + \frac{\kappa - \gamma}{G^\pm} \sinh G^\pm \tau \right] \quad (\text{S24})$$

$$\mathbf{M}_{22}^\pm = \mathbf{M}_{44}^\pm = e^{-\frac{1}{2}(\gamma+\kappa)\tau} \left[\cosh G^\pm \tau - \frac{\kappa - \gamma}{G^\pm} \sinh G^\pm \tau \right] \quad (\text{S25})$$

$$-\mathbf{M}_{21}^- = -\mathbf{M}_{12}^- = \mathbf{M}_{34}^- = \mathbf{M}_{43}^- = \frac{ig e^{-\frac{1}{2}(\gamma+\kappa)\tau}}{G^-} \sinh G^- \tau \quad (\text{S26})$$

$$-\mathbf{M}_{14}^+ = \mathbf{M}_{41}^+ = -\mathbf{M}_{23}^+ = \mathbf{M}_{32}^+ = \frac{ig e^{-\frac{1}{2}(\gamma+\kappa)\tau}}{G^+} \sinh G^+ \tau \quad (\text{S27})$$

with $G^\pm = \sqrt{\pm g^2 + (\kappa - \gamma)^2/4}$.

V. CAVITYLESS SYSTEM

We describe the interaction between the particle motion and the free space electromagnetic mode via the Hamiltonian [2, 5]:

$$H = \frac{p_m^2}{2m} + \frac{1}{2}m\omega_m^2 x_m^2 + \int d\omega \omega a_\omega^\dagger a_\omega - G \int d\omega x_m (a_\omega^\dagger + a_\omega) \quad (\text{S28})$$

The NP is dispersively coupled to the optical field denoted by the operators a_ω and a_ω^\dagger with optomechanical coupling constant G . In this Hamiltonian, the term $a_\omega^\dagger a_\omega$ has units of s^{-1} and determines the probability per unit time to count a photon at specified frequency ω and time t . The NP is also driven by thermal force. Therefore, we include an effective thermal bath to consider these additional fluctuating forces. The corresponding Heisenberg-Langevin equations of motion are given by

$$\dot{x} = \omega_m p, \quad (\text{S29a})$$

$$\dot{p} = -\omega_m x - \gamma p + g \int d\omega (a_\omega^\dagger + a_\omega) + \xi(t), \quad (\text{S29b})$$

$$\dot{a}_\omega = -i\omega a_\omega + igx. \quad (\text{S29c})$$

Here $x = \sqrt{m\omega_m} x_m$ and $p = p_m/\sqrt{m\omega_m}$ are the dimensionless position and momentum operators. Eq. (S29c) can be integrated to have a formal solution for the optical mode operator $a_\omega(t)$. The solutions depend on whether the initial conditions at time $t_- < t$ (the input) or in terms of the final conditions at times $t_+ > t$, (the output) are chosen and are given by

$$a_\omega(t) = a_\omega(t_-) e^{i\omega(t_- - t)} + ig \int_{t_-}^t ds x(s) e^{i\omega(s - t)}, \quad (\text{S30a})$$

$$a_\omega(t) = a_\omega(t_+) e^{i\omega(t_+ - t)} - ig \int_t^{t_+} ds x(s) e^{i\omega(s - t)}, \quad (\text{S30b})$$

where in each equation the first term describes the free evolution of the optical modes, and the second term arises from their interaction with the NP. By defining mechanical mode vector of operators $\mathbf{r}_m(t) = [p(t), 0, x(t), 0]^T$, and eliminating the optical mode operators $a_\omega(t)$ by substituting the formal solution of $a_\omega(t)$ into Eq. (S29b), we have

$$\dot{\mathbf{r}}_m(t) = \mathbf{A}_m \mathbf{r}_m(t) + \mathbf{N}_{\text{in}}, \quad (\text{S31})$$

$$\mathbf{A}_m = \begin{pmatrix} -\gamma & 0 & -\omega_m & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \omega_m & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (\text{S32})$$

$$\mathbf{N}_{\text{in}} = [\xi(t) + \sqrt{4\Gamma} X_{\text{in}}(t), 0, 0, 0]^T, \quad (\text{S33})$$

where $X_{\text{in}}(t) = (a_{\text{in}}(t) + a_{\text{in}}^\dagger(t))/\sqrt{2}$ is the input amplitude quadrature with

$$a_{\text{in}}(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int d\omega a_\omega(t_-) e^{i\omega(t_- - t)}, \quad (\text{S34a})$$

$$a_{\text{out}}(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int d\omega a_\omega(t_+) e^{i\omega(t_+ - t)}. \quad (\text{S34b})$$

Here $\xi(t)$ is the effective thermal force with correlations $\langle \xi(t)\xi(t') \rangle = 2\gamma(\bar{n} + 1/2)\delta(t - t')$. The operators $X_{\text{out}}(t)$ and $Y_{\text{out}}(t)$ describe the transmitted output quadratures and are given by the input-output relation

$$X_{\text{out}}(t) = X_{\text{in}}(t), \quad (\text{S35a})$$

$$Y_{\text{out}}(t) = Y_{\text{in}}(t) + \sqrt{4\Gamma}x(t), \quad (\text{S35b})$$

where $\Gamma = 2\pi G^2 x_{zpf}^2$ is the quantum backaction decoherence rate. The solution for the mechanical mode operators $\mathbf{r}_m(t) = [p(t), 0, x(t), 0]^T$ are then given by

$$\mathbf{r}_m(\tau) = \mathbf{M}(\tau)\mathbf{r}_m(0) + \int_0^\tau ds \mathbf{M}(\tau - s)\mathbf{N}_{\text{in}}(s) \quad (\text{S36})$$

where we have defined $\mathbf{M}(\tau) = \exp[\mathbf{A}_m\tau]$ with elements

$$\mathbf{M}_{11}(\tau) = e^{-\gamma\tau/2} \left(\cos \Omega\tau - \frac{\gamma}{2\Omega} \sin \Omega\tau \right), \quad (\text{S37})$$

$$\mathbf{M}_{33}(\tau) = e^{-\gamma\tau/2} \left(\cos \Omega\tau + \frac{\gamma}{2\Omega} \sin \Omega\tau \right), \quad (\text{S38})$$

$$\mathbf{M}_{13}(\tau) = -\mathbf{M}_{31}(\tau) = \frac{\omega_m}{\Omega} e^{-\gamma\tau/2} \sin \Omega\tau, \quad (\text{S39})$$

$$\mathbf{M}_{22}(\tau) = \mathbf{M}_{44}(\tau) = 1. \quad (\text{S40})$$

With $\Omega = \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{4\omega_m^2 - \gamma^2}$. Input and output light temporal modes are then defined in the same fashion as Eq. (17) with a rectangular temporal mode.

$$[\mathcal{X}_{\text{in,out}}(\tau), \mathcal{Y}_{\text{in,out}}(\tau)] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\tau}} \int_0^\tau [X_{\text{in,out}}(t), Y_{\text{in,out}}(t)] dt \quad (\text{S41})$$

We then write $\mathbf{u}_q(\tau) = [p(\tau), \mathcal{Y}_{\text{out}}(\tau), x(\tau), \mathcal{X}_{\text{out}}(\tau)]^T$ to calculate the covariance matrix for the cavityless system.

VI. ELEMENTS OF COVARIANCE MATRIX

This section is devoted to the evaluation of the CM elements. In calculating the covariance matrix, we deal with three different types of elements.

A. Cavity-based system

First, the mechanical elements are calculated according to

$$\mathbf{V}_{i'i'}(\tau) = \mathbf{M}_{ij}(\tau)\mathbf{M}_{i'j'}(\tau)\mathbf{V}_{jj'}(0) + \int_0^\tau ds \mathbf{M}_{ij}(\tau - s)\mathbf{M}_{i'j'}(\tau - s)\mathbf{N}_{jk}\mathbf{N}_{j'k'}\mathbf{V}_{kk'}^{\text{in}} \quad (\text{S42})$$

while cross-correlation between optical and mechanical modes are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{V}_{i'i'}(\tau) = & \sqrt{2\kappa}\mathbf{M}_{ij}(\tau)\mathbf{V}_{jj'}(0) \int_0^\tau ds' f(s')\mathbf{M}_{i'j'}(s') - \mathbf{V}_{kk'}^{\text{in}} \int_0^\tau ds \mathbf{M}_{ij}(\tau - s)\mathbf{N}_{jk}f(s) \\ & + \sqrt{2\kappa}\mathbf{V}_{kk'}^{\text{in}} \int_0^\tau ds \mathbf{M}_{ij}(\tau - s)\mathbf{N}_{jk} \int_s^\tau ds' f(s')\mathbf{M}_{i'j'}(s' - s)\mathbf{N}_{j'k'} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S43})$$

and finally, optical correlations have the following form

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{V}_{ii'}(\tau) = & \mathbf{V}_{ii'}^{\text{in}} + 2\kappa \mathbf{V}_{jj'}(0) \int_0^\tau ds ds' f(s) f(s') \mathbf{M}_{i'j'}(s) \mathbf{M}_{ij}(s') - 2\sqrt{2\kappa} \mathbf{V}_{ii'}^{\text{in}} \int_0^\tau ds f(s) \int_s^\tau ds' f(s') \mathbf{M}_{i'j'}(s' - s) \mathbf{N}_{j'k'} \\ & + 2\kappa \mathbf{V}_{kk'}^{\text{in}} \int_0^\tau ds \int_s^\tau \int_s^\tau ds' ds'' f(s) f(s'') \mathbf{M}_{i'j'}(s' - s) \mathbf{M}_{i'j'}(s'' - s) \mathbf{N}_{jk} \mathbf{N}_{j'k'} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S44})$$

B. Cavityless system

The mechanical correlations can be calculated as

$$\mathbf{V}_{ii'}(\tau) = \mathbf{M}_{ij}(\tau) \mathbf{M}_{i'j'}(\tau) \mathbf{V}_{jj'}(0) + \int_0^\tau ds \mathbf{M}_{ij}(\tau - s) \mathbf{M}_{i'j'}(\tau - s) \mathbf{V}_{kk'}^{\text{in}} \quad (\text{S45})$$

The cross-correlation between the rectangular temporal optical and mechanical modes are evaluated by

$$\mathbf{V}_{i2}(\tau) = \mathbf{V}_{2i}(\tau) = \sqrt{\frac{4\Gamma}{\tau}} \left\{ \mathbf{M}_{ij}(\tau) \mathbf{V}_{jj'}(0) \int_0^\tau ds' \mathbf{M}_{3j}(s') + [2\gamma(\bar{n} + 1/2) + 2\Gamma] \int_0^\tau \int_0^\tau ds ds' \mathbf{M}_{31}(s' - s) \mathbf{M}_{i1}(\tau - s) \right\}, \quad (\text{S46})$$

$$\mathbf{V}_{i4}(\tau) = \mathbf{V}_{4i}(\tau) = \sqrt{\frac{\Gamma}{\tau}} \int_0^\tau ds \mathbf{M}_{i1}(\tau - s), \quad (\text{S47})$$

and finally, optical correlations are

$$\mathbf{V}_{22}(\tau) = \mathbf{V}_{22}^{\text{in}} + \mathbf{V}_{jj'}(0) \frac{4\Gamma}{\tau} \int_0^\tau ds \int_0^\tau ds' \mathbf{M}_{3j}(s) \mathbf{M}_{3j'}(s') + \frac{4\Gamma[2\gamma(\bar{n} + 1) + 2\Gamma]}{\tau} \int_0^\tau dt \int_0^t ds \int_s^\tau ds' \mathbf{M}_{31}(s' - s) \mathbf{M}_{31}(t - s) \quad (\text{S48})$$

$$\mathbf{V}_{44}(\tau) = \mathbf{V}_{44}^{\text{in}} \quad (\text{S49})$$

$$\mathbf{V}_{42}(\tau) = \mathbf{V}_{24}(\tau) = \frac{4\Gamma}{\tau} \mathbf{V}_{44}^{\text{in}} \int_0^\tau ds' \int_0^{s'} ds \mathbf{M}_{31}(s' - s) \quad (\text{S50})$$

VII. DERIVATION OF MECHANICAL WIGNER FUNCTION

The covariance matrix defined in Eq. (27) can be related to the covariance matrix of the quadratures according to $\mathbf{V}_q = \mathbf{\Omega} \mathbf{V} \mathbf{\Omega}^\dagger$. We then relate the Wigner function to the covariance matrix in the quadratures space according to

$$W(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}; \rho_{AB}) = \frac{1}{\pi^2 \sqrt{\det(\mathbf{V}_q)}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{u}_q^T \mathbf{V}_q^{-1} \mathbf{u}_q\right). \quad (\text{S51})$$

The density matrix can be written in the basis of coherent states as

$$\rho_{AB} = \frac{1}{\pi^4} \int d^2\alpha d^2\beta |\beta\rangle \langle \beta | \rho_{AB} | \alpha \rangle \langle \alpha |, \quad (\text{S52})$$

where $|\alpha\rangle = |\alpha_1, \alpha_2\rangle$ and $|\beta\rangle = |\beta_1, \beta_2\rangle$. Wigner-Weyl transform $W_{\alpha,\beta}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q})$ of the operator $|\beta\rangle \langle \alpha|$

$$\begin{aligned} W_{\alpha,\beta}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}) = & 4 \exp \left[-\frac{|\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2}{2} - \alpha^T \beta^* - \mathbf{p}^T \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{q}^T \mathbf{q} \right. \\ & \left. + \sqrt{2} \alpha^T (\mathbf{q} - i\mathbf{p}) + \sqrt{2} \beta^\dagger (\mathbf{q} + i\mathbf{p}) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S53})$$

allows us to proceed from the Wigner function to the elements of the density matrix in the coherent state representation by calculating a four-dimensional overlap integral [6, 7]

$$\langle \beta | \rho_{AB} | \alpha \rangle = \frac{1}{4\pi^2} \int d\mathbf{p} d\mathbf{q} W_{\alpha, \beta}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}) W(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}; \rho_{AB}) \quad (\text{S54})$$

We use Eq. (S51) and perform a Gaussian integration to obtain

$$\rho_{AB} = \frac{\mathcal{P}_0}{\pi^4} \int d^2\alpha d^2\beta |\beta\rangle \langle \alpha | e^{-\frac{1}{2}|\tilde{\mathbf{s}}|^2 + \frac{1}{2}\tilde{\mathbf{s}}^T \tilde{\mathbf{R}} \tilde{\mathbf{s}}}. \quad (\text{S55})$$

With $\tilde{\mathbf{s}} = (\beta_1^*, \beta_2^*, \alpha_1, \alpha_2)^T$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{R}}$ being a 4×4 symmetric complex matrix written in terms of \mathbf{V} as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{R}} = \boldsymbol{\Omega}^T \boldsymbol{\Omega} (2\mathbf{V} - \mathbf{I}_4) (2\mathbf{V} + \mathbf{I}_4)^{-1}, \quad (\text{S56})$$

$$\mathcal{P}_0 = \frac{4}{\sqrt{\det(2\mathbf{V} + \mathbf{I}_4)}}. \quad (\text{S57})$$

The unnormalized density matrix $\tilde{\rho}_B(n_2)$ of the mechanical mode can be found by taking the state ρ_{AB} and projecting it onto the detected optical mode $|n_2\rangle$. By performing this projection of the state onto $|n_2\rangle$, we obtain $\tilde{\rho}_B(n_2)$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\rho}_B(n_2) &= \langle n_2 | \rho_{AB} | n_2 \rangle \\ &= \frac{\mathcal{P}_0}{\pi^4} \int d^2\alpha_1 d^2\beta_1 d^2\alpha_2 d^2\beta_2 |\beta_1\rangle \langle \alpha_1 | \langle n_2 | \beta_2 \rangle \langle \alpha_2 | n_2 \rangle \\ &\quad \times \exp\left(-\frac{|\tilde{\mathbf{s}}|^2}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\tilde{\mathbf{s}}^T \tilde{\mathbf{R}} \tilde{\mathbf{s}}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S58})$$

For a coherent state $|\alpha_2\rangle = e^{-|\alpha_2|^2/2} \sum_{n_2=0}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha_2^{n_2}}{\sqrt{n_2!}} |n_2\rangle$ the product $\langle n_2 | \beta_2 \rangle \langle \alpha_2 | n_2 \rangle$ can be calculated as

$$\langle n_2 | \beta_2 \rangle \langle \alpha_2 | n_2 \rangle = \frac{1}{n_2!} e^{-(|\alpha_2|^2 + |\beta_2|^2)/2} (\alpha_2^* \beta_2)^{n_2}, \quad (\text{S59})$$

To perform the integration, we define vector $\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{P}\tilde{\mathbf{s}} = (\beta_1^*, \alpha_1, \beta_2^*, \alpha_2)^T = (\mathbf{s}_m, \mathbf{s}_c)^T$, where \mathbf{s}_m and \mathbf{s}_c are vectors corresponding to the mechanical mode and optical modes, respectively and \mathbf{P} is the permutation matrix. Correspondingly, we define a new symmetric matrix \mathbf{R} as

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{P}\tilde{\mathbf{R}}\mathbf{P}^T = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{mm} & \mathbf{R}_{mc} \\ \mathbf{R}_{cm} & \mathbf{R}_{cc} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{S60})$$

where \mathbf{R}_{mm} and \mathbf{R}_{cc} are 2×2 symmetric matrices corresponding to the mechanical and optical modes respectively and \mathbf{R}_{mc} is a 2×2 matrix that connects the two modes. Since \mathbf{R} is symmetric, $\mathbf{R}_{cm} = \mathbf{R}_{mc}^T$.

$$\begin{aligned} |\tilde{\mathbf{s}}|^2 &= |\mathbf{s}_m|^2 + |\mathbf{s}_c|^2, \\ \tilde{\mathbf{s}}^T \tilde{\mathbf{R}} \tilde{\mathbf{s}} &= \mathbf{s}_m^T \mathbf{R}_{mm} \mathbf{s}_m + \mathbf{s}_c^T \mathbf{R}_{cc} \mathbf{s}_c + 2 \mathbf{s}_m^T \mathbf{R}_{mc} \mathbf{s}_c, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S61})$$

Inserting Eqs. (S59) and (S61) into Eq. (S58), the unnormalized density matrix $\tilde{\rho}_B(n)$ can be written as

$$\tilde{\rho}_B(n_2) = \frac{1}{\pi^2} \int d^2\alpha_1 d^2\beta_1 |\beta_1\rangle \langle \alpha_1 | F(\alpha_1, \beta_1), \quad (\text{S62})$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} F(\alpha_1, \beta_1) &= \frac{\mathcal{P}_0}{\pi^2 n_2!} e^{-\frac{1}{2}|\mathbf{s}_m|^2 + \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{s}_m^T \mathbf{R}_{mm} \mathbf{s}_m} \int d^2\alpha_2 d^2\beta_2 (\alpha_2^* \beta_2)^{n_2} e^{-|\mathbf{s}_c|^2 + \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{s}_c^T \mathbf{R}_{cc} \mathbf{s}_c + \mathbf{s}_c^T \mathbf{R}_{cm} \mathbf{s}_m} \\ &= \frac{\mathcal{P}_0}{n_2!} e^{-\frac{1}{2}|\mathbf{s}_m|^2 + \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{s}_m^T \mathbf{R}_{mm} \mathbf{s}_m} \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha_2 \partial \beta_2^*} \right)^{n_2} e^{-|\mathbf{s}_c|^2 + \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{s}_c^T \mathbf{R}_{cc} \mathbf{s}_c + \mathbf{s}_c^T \mathbf{R}_{cm} \mathbf{s}_m} \Big|_{\mathbf{s}_c=0}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S63})$$

We next calculate the unnormalized characteristic function $\chi_B^{n_2}(\beta)$

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_B^{n_2}(\beta) &= e^{-\frac{|\beta|^2}{2}} \text{Tr}(e^{-\beta^* a} \tilde{\rho}_B(n_2) e^{\beta a^\dagger}) \\ &= \frac{e^{-\frac{|\beta|^2}{2}}}{\pi^2} \int d^2\alpha_1 d^2\beta_1 e^{\beta \alpha_1^* - \beta^* \beta_1} \langle \alpha_1 | \beta_1 \rangle F(\alpha_1, \beta_1), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S64})$$

FIG. S3. Non-classical depth as a function of initial thermal occupation of the mechanical oscillator n_0 . (a) Phonon-added (blue lines) and subtracted (red lines) and (b) cavityless system. Each curve corresponds to a different mechanical state marked in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. The upper bound corresponds to a perfect single phonon state shown by the dashed gray line.

In the coherent state basis, the Wigner function for the single-mode state is defined as

$$W_B^{n_2}(\alpha, \rho_B) = \frac{1}{\pi^2} \int d^2\beta e^{-\beta\alpha^* + \alpha\beta^*} \chi_B^{n_2}(\beta), \quad (\text{S65})$$

Substituting $\chi_B^{n_2}(\beta)$ from Eq. (S64) into the definition of Wigner function Eq. (S65) we find the unnormalized Wigner function as

$$\begin{aligned} W_B^{n_2}(\alpha) &= \frac{1}{\pi^4} \int d^2\alpha_1 d^2\beta_1 d^2\beta \langle \alpha_1 | \beta_1 \rangle F(\alpha_1, \beta_1) e^{-|\beta|^2/2} e^{-\beta^*(\beta_1 - \alpha) + \beta(\alpha_1^* - \alpha^*)} \\ &= \frac{2}{\pi^3} e^{-2|\alpha|^2} \int d^2\alpha_1 d^2\beta_1 F(\alpha_1, \beta_1) e^{-\frac{|\alpha_1|^2}{2} - \frac{|\beta_1|^2}{2} - \alpha_1^* \beta_1 + 2(\alpha \alpha_1^* + \alpha^* \beta_1)}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S66})$$

where in the last equality we have performed the integration over β and used the relation $\langle \alpha_1 | \beta_1 \rangle = e^{-|\alpha_1|^2/2 - |\beta_1|^2/2 + \alpha_1^* \beta_1}$. By substituting the function $F(\alpha_1, \beta_1)$ of Eq. (S63) into Eq. (S66), interchanging the order of partial derivatives and integration, and then performing the integration over α_1 and β_1 , we arrive at the final expression of Eq. (29) in the main text for the unnormalized Wigner function of the mechanical mode.

VIII. NON-CLASSICALITY OF HERALDED MECHANICAL STATES

To complete our evaluation of the heralded mechanical states, we use the following two algebraic inequalities to certify nonclassicality from a few Fock-state probabilities that are well-suited to experimental implementations [8]:

$$Q_1^2 > 2Q_0Q_2, \quad (\text{S67})$$

$$Q_0 + \frac{Q_1^2}{2Q_2} \left[\exp\left(\frac{2Q_2}{Q_1}\right) - 1 \right] > 1. \quad (\text{S68})$$

We have checked that only criterion inequality (S67) is capable of detecting the non-classicality of the generated state, while inequality (S68) is not applicable.

Similarly to QNG depth, we define the quantum non-classical depth, d_{NC} , quantifying the amount of heating required to reach the non-classical boundary given by Eqs. (S67) and (S68). It is worth noting that for an ideal single phonon state $\rho_B = |1\rangle\langle 1|$, the non-classical depth is found to be $d_{NC} = 0.646$, represented by a dashed gray line. Fig. S3 shows the non-classical depth versus the initial mechanical occupation for various mechanical states marked in Figs. 2 and 3. This value is approximately twice the magnitude of the corresponding non-Gaussian depth.

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